

Comparing the MSI table with flight data

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Data treatment

Relative (frame-wise) MSI corrections have been determined from 19 transits of bright stars ($H_p \sim 2-3$), using the method described in NDAC/LO/133. The transits are identified in Table 1.

Because of the brightness of the stars, special attention was given to the intensity transfer function (ITF). The photon counts n (per sample) obtained by inversion of the semi-logarithmic coding were corrected for saturation effects (pulse counter dead time) according to the formula $n_{\text{corr}} = n/(1 - n\tau)$, where τ is the dead time in units of the sample interval $1/1200$ s. Preliminary reductions assuming different dead times showed that $\tau \simeq 1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ gave the most constant modulation coefficients M_1 and M_2 as function of magnitude (the red star 72607 was not used in this comparison). All results described below were obtained with this value for the dead time but without any other ITF correction.

Some statistics were also calculated for the ratio of the observed (corrected) count over the count expected from a fitted light curve, as function of the position of the sample relative to the IFOV repositioning. The following mean ratios were obtained from analysis of some 2300 cases (the values in parentheses are the rms dispersion of individual ratios about the mean ratio):

- for the last sample before repositioning: 0.9970 (0.058)
- for the first sample after repositioning: 0.9162 (0.073)
- for the 2nd sample after repositioning: 0.9995 (0.062)
- for the 3rd sample after repositioning: 1.0017 (0.060)
- for the 9th sample after repositioning: 1.0015 (0.058)

The statistical uncertainty of the mean ratios is about 0.0015, so the deviations for the last, 2nd, 3rd and 9th sample are not significant. For the first sample an average IFOV settling time of $70 \mu\text{s}$ is obtained. The increased dispersion of ratios for the first sample indicates that the settling time is not constant, but varies by some $35 \mu\text{s}$ rms around the mean value. Subsequent results were obtained with the first sample rejected.

In order to reduce the IDT data one needs to have a reference grid coordinate G_k for each sample. For the present analysis, this was computed in a slightly different (and more rigorous) way than in NDAC/LO/133, namely by iterative adjustment over a whole transit. In each iteration, G_k was represented as a cubic polynomial fitted to the nine or ten mid-frame grid coordinates obtained in the previous iteration. (A cubic polynomial was always sufficient to get reasonably small residuals.) New mid-frame coordinates were then derived by frame-wise ML estimation of the five signal parameters, and the process iterated until no further changes occurred. Starting values for the mid-frame grid coordinates were obtained as the RGO phases plus an integer slit number, derived from a preliminary estimate of the modulation frequency directly from the photon counts. Do note however that the final results are completely independent of the RGO phases.

Table 1 Data for the 19 transits used in the analysis (N = number of frames in the transit; J = transverse scanfield index for the first frame).

Transit No.	INCA No.	H_p	$B-V$	Field	First frame	N	J
1	60965	2.92	-0.06	F	11517488	10	1
2	56561	3.09	-0.05	P	11520033	10	28
3	56561	3.09	-0.05	F	11520614	10	29
4	60965	2.92	-0.06	F	11521088	10	4
5	65378	2.07	0.03	F	11521812	10	8
6	56561	3.09	-0.05	P	11523633	10	21
7	60965	2.92	-0.06	P	11524108	10	8
8	56561	3.09	-0.05	F	11524213	9	23
9	60965	2.92	-0.06	F	11524688	10	12
10	65378	2.07	0.03	P	11524832	10	25
11	65378	2.07	0.03	F	11525412	10	28
12	56561	3.09	-0.05	P	11527234	9	15
13	60965	2.92	-0.06	P	11527708	10	17
14	56561	3.09	-0.05	F	11527814	10	10
15	60965	2.92	-0.06	F	11528288	10	17
16	60965	2.92	-0.06	P	11531309	9	17
17	60965	2.92	-0.06	F	11531888	10	21
18	72607	2.40	1.72	P	11532243	9	21
19	72607	2.40	1.72	F	11532822	10	25

Table 2 Sample correlation coefficient (r), regression coefficient (c), unit weight residual (t) and weighted post-fit residual (R in nm) for regression of derived MSI corrections against tabulated values for different orientation cases (2, 4, 6 and 8). The weighted pre-fit residual was 17.358 nm.

Case	r	c	t	R
Regression against MSI values from ESA-HIP-09894:				
2	0.178 ± 0.022	0.301 ± 0.030	1.2334	17.080
4	0.235 ± 0.022	0.425 ± 0.032	1.2184	16.872
6	0.041 ± 0.022	0.072 ± 0.031	1.2524	17.343
8	0.027 ± 0.022	0.049 ± 0.031	1.2530	17.351
Regression against modified MSI values:				
2	0.191 ± 0.022	0.371 ± 0.034	1.2305	17.039
4	0.252 ± 0.022	0.504 ± 0.035	1.2130	16.797
6	0.026 ± 0.022	0.055 ± 0.036	1.2531	17.352
8	0.019 ± 0.022	0.038 ± 0.036	1.2533	17.355

Having determined G_k for a whole transit (without application of MSI corrections), the photon count residuals were analysed in terms of MSI as described in NDAC/LO/133. The corrections thus derived have been compared with the MSI table from ESA-HIP-09894, and also with a *modified* MSI table. This was obtained by subtracting, from the original MSI table, a running mean of 19 adjacent scanfields (in the scanning direction). The modified MSI table should be better comparable to the derived values, since the latter are relative within each frame, and since the star travels some 18 or 19 scanfields in the course of one frame.

Results

Corrections were obtained for 2068 scanfields with formal standard errors ranging from 4.7 nm to 95 nm. The median standard error was 18.1 nm. The improvement compared with NDAC/LO/133 is a factor 2.5 in the standard errors, which is exactly what to expect since the stars are now about two magnitudes brighter.

The results of the regressions of the derived versus tabulated MSI are shown in Table 2. Case 4 (nominal orientations of G and H axes) gives strongest correlation and the largest coefficient; the difference with respect to Case 2 is on the 3σ level. (I shall return later to the question why the regression coefficient is not closer to 1.) The reduction in χ^2 from Case 2 to Case 4 is about 60 units, which is highly significant. Already from this analysis we can therefore conclude that Case 4 is the correct orientation. In the following I do not further consider Case 6 and 8.

The figures show the derived corrections with formal standard errors less than 13 nm (about 500 scanfields) plotted against the modified tabulated MSI in Case 2 and 4.

Another way of comparing the three cases 0 (no MSI correction), 2 and 4 is to look at the goodness-of-fit of the photon counts to the light curves before and after application of the tabulated MSI. The total χ^2 for all transits was found to be:

- in Case 0: 113278.71
- in Case 2: 113455.71
- in Case 4: 113242.46

The decrease by some 233 units from Case 2 to 4 is very significant. The average modulation coefficients were found to be:

- in Case 0: $M_1 = 0.7421385$, $M_2 = 0.2697321$
- in Case 2: $M_1 = 0.7421348$, $M_2 = 0.2697329$
- in Case 4: $M_1 = 0.7421398$, $M_2 = 0.2697361$

Although the modulation coefficients are obviously quite insensitive to MSI, the results again support Case 4.

Finally I have looked at the rms residuals of the mid-frame grid coordinates after fitting a cubic polynomial to each transit. The results are given in Table 3. This shows that both Case 2 and 4 give reduced residuals compared with Case 0, but gives no clear indication which of the two cases to prefer. It can be added that the average standard error of the mid-frame grid coordinates (calculated as the formal standard error from the ML estimation, times the unit weight standard error, if the latter exceeds unity) is 1.10 milli-arcsec. The fit to the cubic polynomial is, therefore, as good as can be expected from photon noise alone: there is no evidence of any extraneous error source (such as attitude irregularities) above a fraction of a milli-arcsec.

A closer look at the MSI table

With the present material, the regression of derived MSI corrections versus tabulated ones (modified or not) never gave a linear coefficient greater than about 0.52. This was at first sight surprising, especially since I got values close to unity in my previous note (that result now seems to be entirely spurious). On closer examination, this is in fact a very interesting result, since it gives a very good clue as to the accuracy of the tabular values.

Consider the linear regression of a centred random variable $y = f + \eta$ against the centred variable $x = f + \xi$. Here, f is the underlying common 'factor', while η and ξ are errors on x and y . In our case, f are the true MSI, ξ are the errors in the tabulated values, and η are the errors in the derived values. The coefficient k obtained by least-squares solution of the equations $y = kx + (\text{noise})$ is given by

$$k = \langle xy \rangle / \langle x^2 \rangle \\ = \langle f^2 + f\xi + f\eta + \xi\eta \rangle / \langle f^2 + 2f\xi + \xi^2 \rangle$$

Assuming that the derived and tabulated errors are independent of each other and of the true MSI, we find that

$$k = \sigma_f^2 / (\sigma_f^2 + \sigma_\xi^2)$$

which is clearly less than unity if the errors in the tabulated values are significant relative to the true MSI. From the maximum regression coefficient obtained we may conclude that the errors in the tabulated values are only slightly less than the true MSI.

This conclusion actually applies to the *modified* MSI, or to the 'small-scale' MSI that do not influence the mid-frame coordinates appreciably. For the further analysis it is useful to separate the derived and tabulated MSI into three orthogonal components: a 'large-scale' MSI which can be represented by a cubic polynomial over a transit; a 'medium-scale' MSI which is a running mean of 18 or 19 scanfields, after subtraction of the large-scale MSI; and the remaining 'small-scale' MSI. From a number of considerations similar to the previous paragraph I have arrived at a tentative partitioning of the overall tabulated MSI (having an rms value of 10.9 nm) as shown in Table 4. For instance, the medium-scale component (MMSI) is responsible for residuals of the cubic fits in Table 3; the reduction by about 3 nm rms from Case 0 to Case 4 shows that the real MMSI is about 3 nm greater (quadratically) than the error in the tabulated MMSI. On the other hand, the total tabulated MMSI can be derived directly from the MSI table and amounts to about 4 nm. Hence the real MMSI must be about 3.5 nm and its error about 2.0 nm rms.

Conclusions

The analysis of the 19 bright transits shows unambiguously that Case 4 (the nominal one) is the correct orientation of the MSI table. In other words, the transverse scanfield index J in Table 1 (increasing from 1 to 46 in the sense of increasing z_N , H_F and z_F , or decreasing H_E) is the same as the index N_x used in ESA-HIP-09894.

Furthermore, the analysis has indicated that the true MSI has an rms value of about 8.4 nm, and that the current MSI table has an estimated rms error of about 7 nm. This means that application of the tabulated corrections is just marginally meaningful. Whether the corrections are applied or not, the effects on mid-frame phases is less than the photon noise even for stars of $H_p \sim 2$.

Table 3 Rms residuals (in milli-arcsec) of the mid-frame phases after fitting a cubic polynomial to each transit.

Transit No.	Case 0	Case 2	Case 4
1	1.274	1.243	1.614
2	1.573	1.398	1.497
3	1.373	0.929	0.883
4	0.923	0.752	0.837
5	1.723	1.332	1.288
6	1.732	1.676	1.604
7	1.261	0.850	0.779
8	0.629	0.852	0.745
9	0.742	0.692	0.380
10	0.291	0.775	0.874
11	0.777	0.715	0.512
12	1.237	1.257	1.300
13	0.385	0.474	0.386
14	0.505	0.816	0.753
15	1.193	1.030	1.097
16	1.985	1.574	1.840
17	1.083	1.176	1.114
18	0.883	0.567	0.642
19	0.838	0.562	0.384
Mean value	1.074	0.983	0.975
RMS value	1.169	1.041	1.068

Table 4 Tentative partitioning of the tabulated MSI corrections (from ESA-HIP-09894) into real MSI and measurement errors, and into large, medium and small-scale components. All numbers are rms values in nm.

	Real MSI	Measurement error	Tabulated MSI
Small-scale	7.0	6.0	9.2
Medium-scale	3.5	2.0	4.0
Large-scale	3.0	3.0	4.2
All scales	8.4	7.0	10.9

Modified tabulated MSI correction (Case 2) [nm]

Modified tabulated MSI correction (Case 4) [nm]